

Groves along the coast of Sirdayo are shrinking

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Annotation. As a result of the activities of entrepreneurs on the banks of the Syrdarya, groves are shrinking, and as a result, there is a negative impact on flora and fauna and the ecosystem. Water management structures built from the source to the confluence of the Syrdarya and their water consumption.

Key words: Syrdarya, grove, river bed, reservoir, Aral Sea.

In the process of getting to know the water resources of Tashkent region, the Syr Darya flowing through the borders of Bekobod district, where I was born and raised, attracted my attention. The image of the river that I know has changed completely over the past 25-30 years. It's no secret that as the population increases, the water in the river decreases year by year. This huge river is the longest river in Central Asia, after the Amudarya, it is the busiest river. Its length, including the Norin River, is 3020 kilometers. The Syr Darya flows through the territory of Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, and is separated by a dam on the initiative of the Kazakh state in the northern part of the lake Aral, not to that drying "helpless sea" - It flows into the Small Aral. The distance from Arolboyi to Small Aral is 250 km. The importance of this river for our region cannot be expressed in words. The reason we say this is that the following most important structures are connected with the overflowing of the river bed. Today, about 60 large and small hydroelectric stations have been built in the river bed. Large reservoirs such as Tokhtagul, Qairokum, Chordara, and the Aydar-Arnasoy lake system were formed in the Syrdarya basin. In other words, Syrdarya is the source of life for the region. In recent years, the expansion of irrigated land in Central Asia has led to a decrease in river water. Climate change and shrinking glaciers continue to cause major environmental problems in the river basin. The Syrdaryo originates from the Norin River, which flows from Central Tianshan and is formed by the confluence of the Big Norin and Little Norin Rivers. It corresponds to the territory of Tokhtagul district of Jalalabad region of the Republic of Tajikistan. These areas belong to Chuy region. Its source is the glaciers in the mountains. Tokhtagul borders Talas, Chuy and Norin regions.

When the Big Norin and the Little Norin join together, they get the name Norin. Large and small rivers such as Uzun Ahmed, Karasuv, Ona Archa, Otbosh, Olabuka are added to it. The Tokhtagul reservoir is located between the Chotkal and Fergana mountain ranges. This reservoir was built in 1962-75 of the last century. Total water volume is 19.5 km^3 , length is 65 km, width is 12 km, depth is 215 meters. The hydro facility is designed to irrigate an area of 900,000 hectares. Currently, the volume of water is 7 km^3 . The reservoir is named after the famous Kyrgyz poet Tokhtagul Sotilganov. The Tokhtagul hydroelectric station was built in 1961 at the same time as the construction of the hydroelectric power station. Uchkurgon, Kuribsoy, Tokhtagul, Otboshi, Tashkomir and Shamoldisoy hydroelectric power stations were built on the Norin River. The power plant works on the water flow from the Tokhtagul reservoir. Its total capacity is 1.2 mln. 124 kW. hydroelectric plant produces an average of 5 billion kilowatt hours of electricity per year. The Norin river enters the territory of Uzbekistan from the Uchkurgan district of the Namangan region. In Uchkurgan district, water is taken from the river to the big Fergana canal. The canal is the largest hydraulic structure built in the Fergana Valley. The length of the channel is 350 km. and the water consumption is equal to $532 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$. Today, about 200,000 hectares of cultivated land in the countries of Uzbekistan, Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan are being irrigated through the Big Fergana Canal. In the village of Baliqchi of Uchkurgan district, the Norin river and the Black river join and take the name Sirdarya. The area of the river basin is approximately $462,000 \text{ km}^2$, and its main watershed is $219,000 \text{ km}^2$. The river flows through the Beshariq district of the Fergana region to the Sogd region of the Republic of Tajikistan and reaches the Qairakum reservoir. This reservoir is 55 km long and 22 km wide. Today, the water volume of the Qairaqum reservoir is 3 billion 443 million m^3 , and the water inflow into the reservoir is $892 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$. and the output of water is $880 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$.

The reservoir is used to irrigate cultivated fields in Bekobod district of Tashkent region, Syrdarya and Jizzakh regions, and the neighboring Republic of Kazakhstan. The middle course of the river corresponds to the territory of Uzbekistan. "Farhod hydroelectric plant" was built on the banks of the Syrdarya in the city of Bekobod, Tashkent region, with a total capacity of 126 megawatts. It provides electrical energy to Sirdarya region, Bekobod city, Metallurgical Combine of Uzbekistan and "Bekobodcement" plant. Syrdarya flows through Syrdarya region and enters the territory of Kazakhstan. The river reaches Chordara reservoir. Chordara is the largest reservoir in the middle reaches of the Syr Darya, and the water structure was built for irrigation and energy purposes. The reservoir is located in the regions of South Kazakhstan region of the Republic of Kazakhstan and Jizzakh region of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Chordara reservoir was filled with water in 1966, it is 80 km long

and 25 km wide. This huge river flows through Turkestan, Kyzylorda, Baikanur regions and flows into Kichik Arol on Arolboyi. Although we cannot contribute to the increase of the river's water, we can protect the forests along the Syrdarya, its biological diversity, and reproduce and restore the flora and fauna of the forest complex. it is the duty of all of us not to interfere.

But today, the rivers, which were once rich in wildlife and fish, are in danger, and in some cases, there is a possibility that the Small Aral that are found in the middle of the riverbeds will completely disappear.

Law violations were found in 385 out of 544 enterprises surveyed during the environmental control activities conducted by the State Committee for Ecology and Environmental Protection. 70% of violations of the law are due to unauthorized discharge of wastewater into the water body, 20% to illegal mining of sand and gravel, 5% to dumping of waste in unspecified places, and 5% to non-existence of environmental and regulatory documents. "In addition, during the raids conducted around the riverbeds, 918 cases of illegal mining of sand and gravel, dumping and burning of waste in unspecified places were detected and administrative fines of 1 billion 85 million soums were imposed. According to the relevant decision of the President, the mining of sand and gravel materials in the riverbeds will be carried out only by business entities and other organizations involved in the contract under the procedure established by the "Safe River" under the Ministry of Emergency Situations during their cleaning. That is, entrepreneurs can carry out cleaning works in riverbeds with a high risk of flooding and remove excess stones and gravel under appropriate conditions. In practice, businessmen harm the nature of the river and benefit from it.

It has long been known that a violent relationship with rivers and streams has negative consequences. Nevertheless, the topography of the river bed was disturbed as a result of mining sand-gravel mixture in an unmarked place with the equipment belonging to some enterprises. "In 93.5 percent of stone crushing and screening enterprises, there are no concrete ponds or clarifiers intended for the primary treatment of wastewater. There are cases of industrial waste water being dumped directly from the clarifier into open water bodies or the terrain. The laboratory analysis of samples taken from waste water revealed that its content was 74, 100, and 124 times higher than the established standard for solids, respectively, and additional compensation payments were calculated for these enterprises. But the damage done to nature is huge", the official representative admitted that limiting and suspending this type of business activity will have a negative impact on construction works and cause a sharp increase in the price of gravel on the market. But this cannot be an excuse to justify the crime against nature. On September 23, Shavkat

Mirziyoyev signed the decision "On measures to further improve the system of protection of water bodies". According to the text of the document, special attention is being paid to the improvement of the ecological situation in the country, including the protection of water bodies, the rational use of natural resources, as well as the prevention of emergency situations in the event of floods and landslides. At the same time, there are gaps in the legislation for the cleaning of riverbeds and water protection zones, lakes, reservoirs, canals, collectors and other water bodies, as well as sand and gravel in the implementation of work to strengthen their banks. is creating conditions for unauthorized extraction of its materials.

Project documents for cleaning river beds and strengthening riverbanks should be subject to state environmental expertise by the bodies of the State Committee for Ecology and Environmental Protection in accordance with the procedure established by law.

In conclusion, it should be said that the reason for the daily deterioration of the ecosystem is not only the inter-period water distribution conflict, but also due to the continuous quarrying of stones from the banks of the Syr Darya river, in the last 20 years, the river bed has sometimes changed depending on the location of the quarries. It is moving to the right, sometimes to the left, and is changing its course. As a result, the orchards that have existed for many years are several kilometers away from the river bank, and it is a pity that the flora and fauna are becoming scarce due to the lack of water and moisture. However, it is no secret to any of us that some animals living in these forests are included in the Red Book.

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